

PROGRESS OF THE DISTRICT CENTRAL COOPERATIVE BANKS IN HARYANA: AN ANALYSIS OF FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE & PRODUCTIVITY

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ABSTRACT

In India, District Central Co-operative Banks (DCCBs) are recognizable institutions among all co-operative credit institutions. DCCBs occupy a place of significance in the cooperative credit delivery system. They act as a spokesperson of the cooperative movement at district level. The founders of the movement envisioned the role of DCCBs beyond the boundaries of mere financing banks. DCCBs are expected to serve as a financing bank for the primaries in a district, guide them in their day to day operations, supply of necessary manpower and technology wherever it is required, voicing on behalf of primaries at policy level etc. Because of this integrated role, DCCBs are strategically located and integrated with the cooperative system. Through this paper, we tried to study the growth and progress of DCCBs in Haryana (branches, employees, investments, borrowings, deposits, working capital, business, cost of management, credit, NPA etc). Also, the productivity of Banks has been studied in this attempt. To attain the objectives of this study, data has been collected from secondary sources and analyzed by using various statistical tools.

***Keywords:** DCCBs, Haryana, Productivity, Correlation, Financial performance and Productivity.*

1. Introduction

Cooperatives banks are a special type of banking in which people cooperate with each other in development of a bank with a view to promoting their mutual interest. In this banking organisation, people voluntarily cooperate with each other on equal terms to promote their own economic interest. Cooperative Banking Institutions play an important role in meeting the rising credit needs of rural and underdeveloped India. The amount of credit given by these institutions has greater than before. The performance of cooperatives banks however has been less than satisfactory and is deteriorating rapidly. The short term Cooperative Credit Structure (CCS) has a federal three-tier structure with PACS being the grass root level institutions, the Central Banks at the District level (DCCBs) and the apex Bank at the State level (SCB). In the North-Eastern States and smaller States, there are no DCCBs and the SCB purveys credit through its affiliated

PACS (and so the CCS is a two-tier system¹). The year of 2012 has been celebrated as International Year of Co-operatives under the theme 'Co-operative enterprises build a better world'. This has given a great gratitude to the co-operative banks across the world. Further, co-operatives institutions have been playing a vital role in the development of nation and to empower our society (Dr. A.P.J. Abdul Kalam, 2012). For the duration of one hundred fifty years, cooperatives have been found of various types in various countries across the world. All over the world, there are near about nine lakh societies which are functioning in about hundred countries with very significant number of staff members (Shahrbabaki et. al. 2012). Co-operative banks have distinctive position in the rural credit delivery system to needy and weaker section in the nation (Bhagwati Prasad, 2005). In order to fulfill the present requirements of India for financial inclusion, the co-operative banking channel is more appropriate to supply the needs of unbanked segment of our country (Anand Sinha, 2012). They are important instruments for inclusive growth in India. They are also continuing playing considerable role in alleviating and reducing poverty, generating employment opportunities and in providing higher remunerative returns to the farmers or agriculturist (Sh. Sharad Pawar, 2009). In the current environment, it is well recognized that the success of co-operative banks are highly dependent on the productive employment of available resources.

Figure 1 shows the classification of cooperatives banks in India. According to planning commission, "Cooperatives are of great significance for the working of five year plans." Writing about the importance of cooperatives, Dr. Rajender Prasad states that "It is apparent that the movement is very active and alive in India, no doubt, it is facing a variety of problems but all these may be termed as problems of life and growth and not of stagnation."

District Central Cooperatives Banks were established to provide financial assistance to the primary cooperative societies and to help their efficient organisation. These banks have limited liability. All members of the banks constitute General Body. These are managed by the BOD elected every year by the general body on the basis of 'one individual –one vote.' Their membership differs at different places, but generally their number varies between 10-24. To run their affairs, these banks appoint trained staff on salaries. These banks give interest-free loan to the primary agricultural credit societies, but from others interest is charged. District Central Cooperatives Banks maintain a balance amongst various primary societies. Deposits are accepted from the societies with surplus funds and these are given in the form of loans to those societies which are short of funds. These banks sell shares, valuing Rs. 10 to Rs.100 each. District Central Cooperatives Banks accept deposits from the members as well as others. According to cooperatives societies act 1912; District Central Cooperatives Banks are to keep 25% of their profits in the form of Reserve fund.

¹ Retrieved from the website "<https://www.nabard.org/english/home.aspx>"

Figure: 1 Organisation of Cooperative Banks in India

Mehta committee recommended that District Central Cooperatives Banks should keep ‘special sinking loan fund’. District Central Cooperatives Banks take loan at low interest rates from state cooperatives banks, commercial banks and government. In short, these banks have various sources of finance or funds. District Central Cooperatives Banks give loans to individual and the societies. Loans are given to the societies on the basis of their promissory notes. Individual loans are advanced on the basis of securities. District Central Cooperatives Banks also perform general banking function i.e. to accept deposits from the people, transfer of money etc.

2. Review of literature

There have been many studies undertaken regarding DCCBs. Here, an attempt is made to review the related literature.

Fulbag Singh and Balwinder Singh (2006) analyzed the profitability position of the Central Cooperative Bank in Punjab. Two different years have been studied with the help of a framework of Return on Equity (ROE) model. The sample of bank with high business volume and those with low business volume had been tested separately. The study could be concluded that as

far as the profitability performance was concerned, the central Cooperative Bank of Punjab had worked well. **Surya Rao K (2007)** applied ratio such as profitability analysis, productivity analysis, solvency position, and operational efficiency and SWOT analysis. The study revealed through productivity analysis that the rate of deposits per employee has lagged behind that of the loans per employee ratio. Thus there is need on the part of employees to mobilize deposit to meet loans demand in view of disparity in the growth rate in these two ratios. Accordingly the ratio values of deposits per employee, productivity of employees can be improved. The solvency ratios showed that the bank was maintaining an average cash reserve ratio of 11 per cent that is much more than the stipulated ratio of 6 per cent. The operational efficiency ratios concluded the satisfactory performance. Finally SWOT analysis revealed various aspects of the Eluru DCCBs. **Chahal and Singh (2009)** in their study analyzed the productivity of StCBs of Northern region of India. Productivity of Chandigarh State Co-operative Bank Ltd. was found better than the other five StCBs which are followed by Haryana, Himachal Pradesh, Rajasthan and Punjab State Co-operative Bank Ltd respectively. It is also found that Jammu and Kashmir State Co-operative Bank Ltd. had been performing poor in terms of productive parameters during the period of 2003-2007. **Kodan et. al (2010)** measured that productivity of public sector banks had been better than private and foreign sector banks. It was also highlighted that public and private sector banks were working under increasing return to scale and foreign sector banks group was operating under decreasing return to scale. Public and private sector banks were labour intensive and foreign sector banks were capital intensive. **Sequeira (2012)** studied the productivity in co-operative banks of Dakshina Kannada district of Karnataka state for the period of 1990-1998. The productivity of cooperative banks of the district had improved during the period and also co-operative banks which adopted information technology had shown excellent progress. **Hooda, Vijay (2014)** studied the productivity and performance of District Central Co-operative Banks. The study found that employees had worked efficiently for escalating the productivity of their respective banks. He also observed that branch-wise productivity of the banks had been increased with good growth rate. But, employee-wise productivity had been improved with higher rate than the rate of productivity on the basis of branch.

3. Objectives of the study

The study is an attempt to measure the progress and financial performance of DCCBs in Haryana state. It also analyzed the productivity of all DCCBs of Haryana together in terms of per employee and per branch.

4. Null Hypotheses of the Study

H₁: There is no significant relationship between productivity of employees and productivity of branches during the reference period.

H₂: There is no significant relationship between the growth in productivity of employees and productivity of branches during the reference period.

5. Methodology

The study is descriptive and analytical in nature. It highlights the role and performance of DCCBs in Haryana and analyses the productivity and financial performance of these banks.

6. Sampling the study

There were 19 DCCBs in Haryana which have total of 613 branches in March, 2015. The study covers all DCCBs for attaining the objectives.

7. Period covered by the study

A period of thirteen years from 2001-02 to 2013-14 is taken for this study.

8. Tools used for data collection and Analysis

This study is completely based on secondary data and the required information has been collected from the website of National Federation of State Co-operative Banks Ltd. (NAFSCOB). Some journals like Productivity, Indian Journal of Finance, Finance India, Bank Quest etc. have also been accessed to know the relevant variables and research methodology. For the purpose of analyzing the data, average, standard deviation, minima, maxima, Average Compound Growth Rate, Karl Pearson's Correlation Coefficient and Spearman's Rank Correlation have been calculated for the study. SPSS software has been used for calculating the values of CAGRs, Karl Pearson's Correlation Coefficients and Spearman's Rank Coefficients.

9. Scope of the study

In this study, we considered only quantitative aspects of productivity. Qualitative dimensions and determinants of productivity of DCCBs were not studied. These two main aspects may attract the attention of the different researchers particularly for those who are related to this area and it will be also beneficial for various policymakers regarding banking sector in India.

10. Data Analysis, Results and Discussion

It is very indispensable to study the physical and human resources indicators of DCCBs and growth in these indicators. The status of these indicators determines the policy regarding DCCBs in respect to providing employment opportunities and scattering banking business in the country.

10.1 State of Physical and Human Resources of DCCBs

Table 1 depicts the growth in number of banks, their branches and employees. During 2001-2014, the number of banks has been 19 on an average basis.

Table: 1 Status of Physical and Human Resources of DCCBs in Haryana: 2001-2014

Years	No. of Banks	No. of Branches	Total Employees	Branches per Bank	Employees per Bank	Employees per Branch
2001-02	19	346	4890	18	257	14
2002-03	19	369	4746	19	250	13
2003-04	19	372	4868	20	256	13
2004-05	19	376	4761	20	251	13
2005-06	19	374	4049	20	213	11
2006-07	19	381	4540	20	239	12
2007-08	19	561	4676	30	246	8
2008-09	19	602	4572	32	241	8
2009-10	19	609	4290	32	226	7
2010-11	19	613	4150	32	218	7
2011-12	19	612	3797	32	200	6
2012-13	19	606	3087	32	162	5
2013-14	19	613	2915	32	153	5
MEAN	19	495	4257	26	224	9
MAX	19	613	4890	32	257	14
MIN	19	346	2915	18	153	5

Source: NAFSCOB, Mumbai

Further table 1 shows that there are, on an average, 495 branches of DCCBs in India. In 2001-02 there was minimum number of branches and maximum of that was in 2010-11 and 2013-14. One DCCB has had 26 branches on an average during the reference period of time as table under consideration is depicting. But the total employees of these banks reduced during the year of 2001-2014 i.e. from 4890 to 2915. This decline attracts the attention of various policy makers and banking authority. Further, the table also reveals that one DCCB has had total of 224 employees in average basis. This variable is also showing decreasing trend in the providing employment opportunities to people. It is also observed from the analysis that though number of DCCBs branches has been increased but the employees of DCCBs have been reduced during our study period.

10.2 Financial Performances of DCCBs

Financial performance of DCCBs in Haryana can be measured with the help of table 2, 3 and 4. The total deposits have been increased from 2001 to 2014. The average total business was Rs. 1349816 lakh. The total credit was maximum in 2013-14 and minimum in 2001-02. The total borrowings were Rs. 719029 in 2013-14.

Table: 2 Financial Performances of DCCBs in Haryana: 2001-14 (In Lakh)

Years	Total Deposits	Total Business	Total Credit	Total Borrowings
2001-02	166875	487559	313071	160603
2002-03	201398	555651	354253	184687
2003-04	229194	589595	386064	187329
2004-05	238200	646281	408081	200969
2005-06	278630	732628	453998	220501
2006-07	293650	797966	504316	257549
2007-08	330438	882986	552548	300095
2008-09	377860	911548	533688	272545
2009-10	435319	842372	568958	269690
2010-11	493488	1053905	645651	336725
2011-12	533122	7642854	7109732	401152
2012-13	549271	1091618	542347	692841
2013-14	572377	1312649	740272	719029
MEAN	361525	1349816	1008691	323363
S.D	141708.06	1905211.90	1836975.22	182441.63
CAGR (%)	9.95	7.92	6.84	12.22
MAX	572377	1312649	740272	719029
MIN	166875	487559	313071	160603

Source: NAFSCOB, Mumbai

Table 3 depicts the total share capital, total reserve funds, owned funds, total membership, total investments, total loan & advances and total loan outstanding for the period of 2001-02 to 2013-14. The average share capital was Rs. 26671 lakh and reserve funds was Rs. 35988 lakh. The average growth rate of owned funds is 9.88%. The total membership was increased to 40134 lakh in the year of 2014. The maximum and minimum value of total investment was Rs. 417540 lakh and Rs. 43646 lakh respectively. The annual growth rate of total loan & advances and total loan outstanding was 8.69% and 8.13% respectively.

Table: 3 Financial Performances of DCCBs in Haryana: 2001-2014 (In Lakh)

Years	Total Share Capital	Total Reserve Funds	Owned Funds	Total Memberships	Total Investment	Total Loan & Advances	Total Loan Outstanding
2001-02	14616	13885	28501	14200	43646	333958	313148
2002-03	16469	17634	34103	15277	52013	374135	355994
2003-04	17953	23483	41436	16386	56141	435508	386063
2004-05	19236	26319	45555	16729	60115	517031	414368
2005-06	22509	30697	53206	25628	80720	556450	458130
2006-07	24426	33268	57694	31592	91604	592325	517660

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2007-08	42501	40547	83048	33376	108171	675732	566168
2008-09	25361	38854	64215	40908	142023	454418	554088
2009-10	24494	37649	62143	40616	139896	541034	573507
2010-11	29541	46634	76175	42690	200825	693265	659580
2011-12	32372	47828	80200	37761	417540	861929	756164
2012-13	37235	54010	91245	39275	224133	930106	816341
2013-14	40010	57040	97050	40134	240670	987172	864897
MEAN	26671	35988	62659	30352	142884	611774	556624
S.D	9084.60	13428.60	21885.7 9	11184.00	106123.36	208660.79	176390.64
CAGR (%)	8.05	11.48	9.88	8.32	14.03	8.69	8.13
MAX	42501	57040	97050	42690	417540	987172	864897
MIN	14616	13885	28501	14200	43646	333958	313148

Source: NAFSCOB, Mumbai

Table 4 demonstrates the financial performance of DCCBs in Haryana for the period of 2001-14. The average amount of profit was Rs. 1685 lakh. The total working capital was increased to Rs. 1165581 lakh in 2014. The recovery rate was 77.36% in the year 2013-14. The growth rate of cost of management was 9.44%. The average COM to working capital was 3%. The amount of absolute NPA was Rs. 12680 lakh in 2001-02 which increased to Rs. 45157 lakh in 2013-14.

Table: 4 Financial Performances of DCCBs in Haryana: 2001-2014 (In Lakh)

Years	Profits	Total Working Capital (WC)	Recovery (%)	Cost of Management (COM)	COM per Employee	COM to WC (%)	Yield on Employees	Absolute NPA
2001-02	2033	394350	79.26	16059	3.28	4.22	-	12680
2002-03	2737	446869	75.46	12294	2.59	2.77	-	13695
2003-04	6213	491228	80.56	13745	2.82	2.81	-	17873
2004-05	4964	527619	83.77	15574	3.27	3.03	-	-
2005-06	2516	595660	82.14	12949	3.2	2.19	-	-
2006-07	-1418	679491	75.3	17642	3.89	2.74	-	-
2007-08	-594	754691	78.07	20535	4.39	2.8	-	-
2008-09	2203	795417	78.09	30381	6.65	3.75	-	-
2009-10	-966	836580	67.89	30068	6.87	3.8	2934	52674
2010-11	-208	959699	70.81	35343	8.52	3.82	3299	52139
2011-12	-2016	1102560	73.74	37622	9.91	3.69	3243	49505
2012-13	2988	1110548	75.12	49052	15.89	4.42	7945	41210
2013-14	3449	1165581	77.36	51878	17.8	4.45	10420	45157
MEAN	1685	758484	77	26396	7	3	5568	48137
S.D	2539.39	265079.18	4.40	13762.12	5.02	0.74	3416.28	17730.59

CAGR (%)	4.15	8.69	-0.19	9.44	13.89	0.41	-	10.26
MAX	6213	1165581	83.77	51878	17.8	4.45	10420	52674
MIN	-2016	394350	67.89	12294	2.59	2.19	2934	41210

Source: NAFSCOB, Mumbai

Note: (-) Data Not Available.

10.3 Employees' productivity of DCCBs

Table 5 shows the employee productivity of DCCBs during 2001-14. We have considered four indicators of productivity i.e. deposits per employee, business per employee, credit per employee and borrowings per employee. Deposits per employee have been Rs. 92 lakh on an average. The average amount of credit per employee is Rs. 258 lakh during the reference period. The CAGR of all indicators was 14.41%, 12.30%, 11.18% and 16.78% respectively. Business per employee as a variable is considered to know the productivity. It has shown less significant growth as compared to other two variables.

Table: 5 Employee's Productivity of DCCBs in Haryana: 2001-14 (In Lakh)

Years	Deposits per Employee	Business per Employee	Credit per Employee	Borrowings per Employee
2001-02	34	100	64	33
2002-03	42	117	75	39
2003-04	47	121	79	38
2004-05	50	136	86	42
2005-06	69	181	112	54
2006-07	65	176	111	57
2007-08	71	189	118	64
2008-09	83	199	117	60
2009-10	101	196	133	63
2010-11	119	254	156	81
2011-12	140	2013	1872	106
2012-13	178	354	176	224
2013-14	196	450	254	247
MEAN	92	345	258	85
S.D	52.32	510.76	487.74	69.62
CAGR (%)	14.41	12.30	11.18	16.78

Source: NAFSCOB, Mumbai

To measure the associations among the above said four indicators of productivity of DCCBs in Haryana during the study period, Karl Pearson's correlation coefficient is also calculated by

using the software SPSS. It is given in table 6. It shows that there is significant and high degree of relationship at level of 1% exists between business & credit per employee and deposits & borrowings per employee. But there is moderate level of correlation among credit, business and deposits per employee. Further, between borrowings and credit per employee has very low degree of relation.

Table: 6 Correlations Matrix for Deposits per Employee, Credit per Employee, Business per Employee and Borrowings per Employee

		deposits per employee	credit per employee	business per employee	borrowings per employee
deposits per employee	Pearson Correlation	1	.372	.456	.936**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.210	.118	.000
	N	13	13	13	13
credit per employee	Pearson Correlation	.372	1	.996**	.181
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.210		.000	.554
	N	13	13	13	13
business per employee	Pearson Correlation	.456	.996**	1	.271
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.118	.000		.370
	N	13	13	13	13
borrowings per employee	Pearson Correlation	.936**	.181	.271	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.554	.370	
	N	13	13	13	13

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

10.4 Branch Wise Productivity of DCCBs

The next variable of productivity is to calculate and analysis the results of branches expansion by DCCBs during the study period. It is also measured through four indicators deposits per branch, business per branch, borrowings per branch and credit per branch. Table 7 shows that the average amount of deposits per branch is Rs. 711 lakh and business per branch is Rs. 2530 lakh during the study period. The CAGR of credit and borrowings per branch is 2.25% and 7.39% respectively.

Table: 7 Branch Wise Productivity of DCCBs in Haryana: 2001-14 (In Lakh)

Years	Deposits per Branch	Business per Branch	Credit per Branch	Borrowings per Branch
2001-02	482	1409	905	464
2002-03	546	1506	960	501
2003-04	616	1585	1038	504
2004-05	634	1719	1085	534

2005-06	745	1959	1214	590
2006-07	771	2094	1324	676
2007-08	589	1574	985	535
2008-09	628	1514	887	453
2009-10	715	1383	934	443
2010-11	805	1719	1053	549
2011-12	871	12488	11617	655
2012-13	906	1801	895	1143
2013-14	934	2141	1208	1173
MEAN	711	2530	1854	632
S.D	142.43	3001.96	2936.61	243.93
CAGR (%)	5.21	3.27	2.25	7.39

Source: NAFSCOB, Mumbai

Table 8 repeats the correlation coefficient among all four indicators of bank's productivity per branch. There is high degree and significant relation between deposits & borrowings per branch and Credit & business per branch. But there is insignificant relationship between Business & borrowings per branch and credit & borrowings per branch. These associations are both significant and insignificant at the level of 1% significance.

Table: 8 Correlations Matrix for Deposits per Branch, Business per Branch, Credit per Branch and Borrowings per Branch

		deposits per branch	business per branch	credit per branch	borrowings per branch
deposits per branch	Pearson Correlation	1	.393	.356	.776**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.183	.232	.002
	N	13	13	13	13
business per branch	Pearson Correlation	.393	1	.999**	.084
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.183		.000	.785
	N	13	13	13	13
credit per branch	Pearson Correlation	.356	.999**	1	.040
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.232	.000		.896
	N	13	13	13	13
borrowings per branch	Pearson Correlation	.776**	.084	.040	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.002	.785	.896	
	N	13	13	13	13

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

10.5 Test of Hypotheses

The two hypotheses were formulated to verify and achieve the objectives of this study. So, for testing the null hypotheses, Spearman's coefficient of correlation is used.

H₁: H₁: There is no significant relationship between productivity of employees and productivity of branches during the reference period.

Here, we considered business per employee an indicator for employee productivity only and for representing branch wise productivity- business per branch have been considered. Table 9 shows the trends of both variables. Further, correlation matrix is also given to prove the hypothesis. Spearman's correlation coefficient is 0.566. It means that correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed). It concludes that there is high degree positive relationship between productivity of labour and productivity of branch achieved by all DCCBs for the time period under study. The null hypothesis is rejected.

Table: 9 Business per Employee and Business per Branch: Spearman's rank Correlation (In Lakh)

Years	Business per Employee	Business per Branch
2001-02	100	1409
2002-03	117	1506
2003-04	121	1585
2004-05	136	1719
2005-06	181	1959
2006-07	176	2094
2007-08	189	1574
2008-09	199	1514
2009-10	196	1383
2010-11	254	1719
2011-12	2013	12488
2012-13	354	1801
2013-14	450	2141

Source: Calculated by Authors

Correlations Matrix

			business per branch	business per employee
Spearman's rho	business per branch	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.566*
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.044
		N	13	13
	business per employee	Correlation Coefficient	.566*	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.044	.
		N	13	13

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Next, the second hypothesis is tested here. The same methodology is applied for testing the hypothesis. Table 10 shows the growth rate of business per employee and business per branch during the study period.

H₂: There is no significant relationship between the growth in productivity of employees and productivity of branches during the reference period.

Here, correlation coefficient is 0.806. It states that there is high degree and positive relationship between growth rate in per employee productivity and branch wise productivity of DCCBs in Haryana during 2001-14. Hence, null hypothesis is again rejected. It is found that both hypotheses are not accepted as per spearman’s rank correlation for the reference period.

Table: 10 Growth in Business per Employee and Business per Branch: Spearman’s rank Correlation

Years	Growth in Business Per Employee (%)	Growth in Business Per Branch (%)
2001-02	-	-
2002-03	17	7
2003-04	3	5
2004-05	12	8
2005-06	33	14
2006-07	-3	7
2007-08	7	-25
2008-09	6	-4
2009-10	-2	-9
2010-11	29	24
2011-12	693	626
2012-13	-82	-86
2013-14	27	19

Source: Calculated by Authors

Correlations Matrix

			growth in business per employee	growth in business per branch
Spearman's rho	growth in business per employee	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.806**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.001
		N	13	13
	growth in business per branch	Correlation Coefficient	.806**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.001	.
		N	13	13

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Suggestions

Cooperatives have completed nearly 95 years in India. But their progress has been rather very slow. Cooperatives movement has just succeeded in fulfilling only 40% of the credit needs of the farmers. It has covered only 60% of India's population. In the words of Vishvarraya, "All that has been done amounts only to scratching of the surface". Success of this banking system depends upon the various factors i.e. re-organisation of primary societies, supply of capital, integration of long term and short term credit, reforms in debt policy, long term credit, less government control, training to staff members, publicity of cooperatives banks, credit on the basis of crops, re-organisation of cooperative banks, reforms in administration, reserve funds of cooperative societies etc. The district cooperative banking system has served useful role of spreading banking habits throughout the state. However, a majority of cooperative banks is yet to achieve financial viability on sustainable basis despite their long year of existence. Hence, attention is to be paid to reform both rural and urban cooperative banking system.

Conclusion

Banking organizations can be more effective and successful by achieving high level of productivity. In cooperative banking system, DCCBs have great significance. It helps in raising socio economic status of the people. This study finds that DCCBs are working efficiently for improving the productivity of their respective banks as ACGR have proved. It is also found that branches per bank have been increased. But employees per branch have been declined during the study period. Besides, DCCBs need to supply some more impressive benefits to their employees and renovate the infrastructure of branches to make them striking because they are considered as real friends by the farmers in our country. So, these banks should greatly stress on the requirements of that strata of the society. The need of the time is that state and central government should perceive the co-operative banking model as a proper structure for achieving the goals of financial inclusion in India. This system would be economical and provide results rapidly if it is monitored appropriately and the role of DCCBs in Haryana state will be very remarkable for the same.

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